

1 01 Aug 2025

2 RH: Steele and Lashley • Human dimensions of wild turkey hunting

3 **Reviewing human dimensions of wild turkey hunting research and synthesizing future**
4 **directions**

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12 **ABSTRACT** Wild turkey (*Meleagris gallopavo*) hunting has a rich history in the United States,
13 and is important culturally, economically, and for wildlife conservation. However, the wild
14 turkey hunting community faces issues related to recruiting young, diverse hunters, which may
15 face unique barriers compared to other hunting communities. Additionally, the wild turkey
16 hunting community is experiencing several shifts in long-established hunting practices and
17 regulations, the reasons for which could be explored using a human dimensions perspective. We
18 conducted a systematic literature review to better understand the human dimensions of wild
19 turkey hunting. Our review yielded 32 studies from 1985 to 2023, detailing findings from 20
20 states in the United States, mostly in the Southeast. Only 2 studies focused on wild turkey
21 hunters in the western United States (Arizona and Idaho). Demographic findings suggest that the
22 average wild turkey hunter is older (~ 50 years old) than hunters overall (median = 35–44 years

23 old) and indicate less female participation (~94% male) compared to hunters overall (77% male).
24 Most studies assessed hunter satisfaction and hunt quality (59%) or support for regulations
25 (78%). Studies reported consistent concern among hunters regarding their safety. All studies
26 were conducted using questionnaires and <5 % of studies incorporated a theoretical framework
27 into their research. Expanding research to incorporate more qualitative interviews and mixed-
28 method approaches, as well as developing survey instruments to test theoretical frameworks,
29 could greatly benefit human dimensions of wild turkey hunting research. Using these
30 methodological approaches may provide a deeper understanding of the barriers preventing
31 potential new hunters from becoming wild turkey hunters as well as exploring factors
32 influencing motivations and identity factors that could be useful to inform conservation and
33 policy. We recommend incorporating more comprehensive human dimensions research
34 approaches to help address important issues facing wild turkey conservation and the hunting
35 community.

36 **KEYWORDS** demographics, game species, hunters, questionnaires, social science

37 Hunting and angling contribute significant funds to wildlife conservation through the Pittman-
38 Robertson Act, Migratory Bird Hunting and Conservation Stamp Act, Dingell-Johnson Act, and
39 sale of hunting and fishing licenses (Heffelfinger et al. 2013). Hunting also provides critical
40 means of population control of native nuisance species and a tool for management of invasive
41 species (Quirós-Fernández et al. 2017, Hagen et al. 2018, Bender et al. 2019). Despite the
42 importance of hunting to wildlife management and conservation, wildlife agencies and
43 organizations face ongoing issues related to recruiting young, diverse, and nontraditional
44 pathway hunters (Vayer et al. 2021, von Furstenberg et al. 2023). Nontraditional pathway hunters
45 are defined as those who enter the hunting community later in life (e.g., in adulthood), had

46 minimal or no familial or social support for becoming a hunter, and/or belong to largely
47 underrepresented groups within the hunting community (Vayer et al. 2021). While introductory
48 hunting such as deer (*Odocoileus* spp.) hunting may present less barriers when recruiting new
49 hunters, barriers may be exacerbated for introducing new hunters to more intricate forms of
50 hunting such as wild turkey (*Meleagris gallopavo*) hunting (Harmel-Garza et al. 1999).

51 Wild turkey hunting is uniquely challenging in comparison to other forms of hunting
52 because of their exceptional eyesight, intelligence, and vital locations (Dickson 1992). As a
53 result, wild turkey hunting may be intimidating to novice hunters; the average age of first-time
54 wild turkey hunters is commonly in their 30s (Harmel-Garza et al. 1999, Van Why et al. 2001).
55 Additionally, the wild turkey hunting community has not recruited female and racially/ethnically
56 diverse hunters at the same rate compared to other hunting communities, potentially related to
57 these barriers (USFWS 2011, Heyser et al. 2022). Despite barriers to new hunters, wild turkey
58 hunting has the largest approval from the general public among game species (tied with deer;
59 Duda et al. 2019). Hunting wild turkeys in North America dates back thousands of years, and has
60 strong cultural importance, especially in the eastern United States (Dickson 2001, Watkins et al.
61 2018). Wild turkey is the most frequently targeted big game species behind only deer, with 2-
62 million hunters estimated to have targeted wild turkeys according to the United States Fish and
63 Wildlife Service's (USFWS) 2016 National Survey of Fishing, Hunting, and Wildlife-Associated
64 Recreation report (USFWS 2018c). However, the estimated number of wild turkey hunters
65 decreased from 3.1 million in 2011 to 2 million in 2016, and the estimated percentage of hunters
66 that target wild turkeys also decreased from 27 % in 2011 to 22 % in 2016 (USFWS 2018b, c).
67 Although these are estimates and this data was not included in the most recent edition of the
68 USFWS's national survey report in 2022, this decrease in wild turkey hunting effort could be

69 attributed to overall declines in estimated hunting participation or may be partly attributed to
70 shifts in regulatory practices aimed to counteract apparent wild turkey population declines
71 (USFWS 2018c, Chamberlain et al. 2022, Lovett 2023).

72 The wild turkey is native to many regions of North America, and several subspecies of
73 wild turkey have been introduced to new regions of North America, including Hawaii, USA
74 (Chamberlain et al. 2022). While every state except Alaska, USA, has a wild turkey hunting
75 season, regulations vary considerably among states (e.g., access to both a fall/spring season and
76 ability to use different methods of take). For example, while all these 49 states have a spring wild
77 turkey season, only 41 states offer a fall wild turkey season (NWTf 2024). Fall wild turkey
78 season in many states differs largely from spring season because either sex can be legally
79 harvested in the fall, whereas only males are harvested in spring (except for bearded females in
80 some states). Although wild turkeys were historically mainly hunted in fall, many fall wild
81 turkey seasons have been suspended or cancelled since 2000 due to low participation and
82 concern about their effects on the wild turkey population demography given a relatively high
83 proportion of fall harvests are female wild turkeys (NWTf 2021a, 2024; Lovett 2023). In
84 Wisconsin, USA, nearly 50% of the wild turkeys harvested during the 2023 fall wild turkey
85 season were females, while <3% of females are harvested during spring hunting seasons in most
86 cases according to published causes of mortality (Lohr and Finger 2024, Lashley et al. – In-
87 Revision). Another important distinction between states is what methods of take can be used to
88 target wild turkeys depending on the season (fall or spring) and type of land (public or private),
89 with some states permitting wild turkey hunting with rifles in some circumstances. In Virginia,
90 USA, >30% of fall hunters and ~10% of spring hunters reported that they typically target wild
91 turkeys with a rifle (Valdez and White 2024).

92 The variety of state regulations and unique practices of wild turkey hunting have led to an
93 emphasis on hunter safety, especially on high-use public lands (NWTF 2021*b*). Like other avian
94 game species, wild turkeys have excellent eyesight and can see in color (Barber et al. 2006). As a
95 result, hunters are not required to wear hunter orange for safety in most states because this would
96 decrease harvest success. Eriksen et al. (1985) documented a large decrease in the success rate of
97 calling wild turkeys when wearing hunter orange. Despite this, Pennsylvania, USA, implemented
98 hunter-orange requirements for wild turkey hunters in 1992–1993, but findings suggest that
99 while the hunter-orange requirements briefly reduced wild turkey hunting incidents, the number
100 of incidents increased again thereafter (NWTF 2005, Smith et al. 2005). These requirements
101 were eventually removed for Spring in 2008 and Fall in 2019 (Casalena 2018, Liguori 2019). In
102 1991, the National Wild Turkey Federation (NWTF) formed the Wild Turkey Safety Task force
103 to address safety concerns, with nationwide wild turkey hunting incident rates as high as 8.1 per
104 100,000 participants in 1992 (NWTF 2021*b*). Studies in Michigan, Alabama, and Pennsylvania,
105 USA, indicated that hunting incident rates were greater for wild turkey hunting than other game
106 species (Langenau et al. 1985, Kantola et al. 1987, Smith et al. 2005). By 2005, the incident rate
107 had decreased to 2.95 per 100,000 participants (NWTF 2021*b*). However, recent advancements
108 in hunting technology and changes in hunting practices have led to new potential safety
109 concerns. Practices such as ‘fanning’ or ‘reaping’, in which a hunter moves behind a wild turkey
110 tail fan or a decoy into the shooting range of a male, have led to serious injuries (Pearce 2017).
111 New technology such as Tungsten Super Shot (TSS) shotgun ammunition that has a longer
112 effective range, poses a potential risk for hunters to fire more dangerous shots (Miloshewski
113 2024, Whipkey 2025).

114 Since the 1980s, the rapidly changing wild turkey hunting landscape has led to an
115 emphasis from wildlife managers and researchers to document attitudes and perceptions of wild
116 turkey hunters. While state agencies typically collect critical information including hunter effort
117 and success rates from hunters for annual wild turkey harvest reports, a human dimensions
118 approach can be used to collect information about hunter's perceptions of hunting safety risks,
119 changes to hunting regulations, use of decoys, and why they prefer to hunt on public or private
120 land. Additionally, human dimensions of wildlife research also uses theoretical frameworks to
121 examine people's values, norms, and behavioral intentions. Examples of these theoretical
122 frameworks include value-belief-norm theory (Stern 2000), the theory of planned behavior
123 (Ajzen 1985), and the theory of reasoned action (Fishbein 1967, Fishbein and Ajzen 1975).
124 Applying these theoretical frameworks or constructs from these theories to human dimensions
125 research allows for a deeper understanding of how different variables (e.g., values, personal
126 norms, attitudes) influence critical behaviors such as mentoring young hunters and joining
127 hunting organizations. Despite the cultural significance of wild turkey hunting and contributions
128 of wild turkey hunting to wildlife conservation, little information has been gathered about the
129 extent of human dimensions of wild turkey hunting research. To address this information gap,
130 we: 1) conducted a literature review to document historical human dimensions of wild turkey
131 research and assessed trends; and 2) identified gaps in the literature to inform recommendations
132 for future research directions for human dimensions of wild turkey conservation and hunting
133 research.

134 **METHODS**

135 We conducted a systematic literature review, which provides a more rigorous and structured
136 approach to collating and processing available research on a topic (Pullin and Stewart 2006, van

137 Velden et al. 2018, Steele 2023). Our search included both peer-reviewed and ‘grey’ literature
138 (e.g., nonpeer-reviewed conference proceedings, theses, dissertations, agency reports, etc.)
139 because many critical wildlife management documents are not published in scientific journals
140 (Steele 2023). We used a multi-faceted approach to this review involving: 1) the use of search
141 terms “turkey hunters survey”, “turkey hunters questionnaire”, “turkey hunter interview”,
142 “turkey hunting human dimensions”, “turkey hunting survey”, and “turkey hunting social
143 science” on Google and Google Scholar to view publications published before August 2024; 2)
144 reviewing previous publications included in the Proceedings of the National Wild Turkey
145 Symposium; and 3) examining references of each publication we reviewed (i.e., reverse
146 snowballing approach; Steele 2023). This resulted in a total of 57 publications. We then assessed
147 these publications based upon our exclusion criteria, which is vital to ensuring that research
148 accurately fits the objective of the systematic literature review (Pullin and Stewart 2006). Our
149 exclusion criteria required that the central focus of each publication should be the human
150 dimensions of wild turkey hunting; as such, we excluded: 1) state agency harvest reports that
151 only included several questions about management preferences or hunting practices; 2) state
152 agency reports that provided supplemental information to harvest reports while gathering some
153 information about management preferences or hunting practices (see Lusk 2022, Lohr and Finger
154 2023); and 3) studies broadly considering hunting of multiple species (e.g., hunting of deer,
155 waterfowl, and wild turkey). Lastly, we excluded publications focusing mainly on effects of the
156 COVID-19 global pandemic on wild turkey hunting because this emphasis (e.g., impact of
157 lockdown protocols) differed greatly from the other publications included in this review and the
158 overall objective of our literature review (e.g., Phillips et al. 2024).

159 After screening publications based upon our exclusion criteria, we extracted data from
160 these publications and synthesized this data (Pullin and Stewart 2006). We synthesized data
161 regarding the following variables: 1) hunter age; 2) hunter sex; 3) hunter race/ethnicity; 4) use of
162 decoys; 5) states included in the study; 6) years of wild turkey hunting experience; and 7)
163 reported safety concerns. In addition, we also captured if the study used any theoretical
164 framework, who conducted the study (e.g., state agency, university researchers, collaborative
165 effort), and what type of methodology was used (e.g., questionnaire, qualitative interview,
166 mixed-methods, etc.). If a publication provided findings from separate data collection in multiple
167 states or findings from the same state across several years of separate data collection, we
168 included data from these publications as multiple data entries when compiling our dataset. For
169 example, if a publication documented the findings from separate questionnaires implemented in
170 Texas, USA, in 2005, 2010, and 2015, we included this as 3 entries for compiling data. If
171 multiple publications were derived from the same survey document, we only considered this as
172 one data entry (e.g., Maldonado 2017; Schroeder et al. 2018*a, b*, 2019; Watkins et al. 2018;
173 Chapagain et al. 2020). When compiling data for reported safety concerns, we compiled data
174 only from publications that asked similarly framed questions. For example, we included
175 questions addressing concerns for personal safety, if the number of hunters afield presented a
176 safety hazard, and concerns about being shot by another hunter. When compiling data for decoy
177 use, we grouped data into two categories based on level of reported use: 1) general use of
178 decoys; and 2) frequent use of decoys. The general use of decoys category consisted of data from
179 studies that simply reported if the respondent used decoys when hunting or if the study included
180 options for the respondent to describe their level of use (e.g., ‘never’, ‘sometimes’, ‘often’, etc.),
181 we compiled data for respondents who listed any use of decoys. The frequent use of decoys

182 category consisted of data from studies that framed the question using phrasing like ‘do you
183 typically use decoys’ or ‘do you normally use decoys’, along with responses such as ‘always’,
184 ‘usually’, or ‘often’ from studies that included options for the respondent to describe their level
185 of use. When compiling percentages from data entries, a weighted average based on the sample
186 size was included when relevant (for data entries that reported sample size). We compared many
187 variables prior to 2000 (1985-2000) and post-2000 (2001-2023) because several critical changes
188 within the wild turkey hunting community occurred around 2000 (e.g.,
189 legalization/popularization of decoys, changes to safety education and reporting, etc.; Newman
190 2014; NWTF, 2021*b*).

191 **RESULTS**

192 Our review yielded a total of 32 publications, and 44 total data entries (Table S1, available in
193 Supporting Information), covering findings during 1985–2023. A total of 20 states were
194 represented; the majority were southeastern states. Arizona and Idaho were the only western
195 states represented in the literature review. Out of the 42 total data entries, Missouri ($n = 5$),
196 Mississippi ($n = 4$), Ohio ($n = 4$), and Pennsylvania ($n = 4$), USA, were the most represented
197 states (Figure 1). While our literature review compiles data from various human dimensions of
198 wild turkey hunting studies across the U.S. to assess historical trends, our results are skewed
199 towards southeastern states and some trends may be influenced by state and regional differences.
200 Additionally, while we weighted compiled percentages based on sample size when applicable,
201 some of the trends that we identified may still be influenced by differences in sample size.

202 **Demographics and hunter characteristics**

203 Most data entries ($n = 31$; 70%) included the average age of respondents. From 1985–2000 ($n =$
204 16), the compiled average age of hunters was 42 (Figures 2, 3). In contrast, from 2001–2023 ($n =$

205 14), the compiled average age of hunters was 49. The sex of respondents was captured in 20 of
206 44 studies; only one data entry had a sample that was <90% male. Of the studies published since
207 2014 ($n = 10$), 40% reported race/ethnicity, of which only one study indicated a sample that was
208 <90% white. Many studies ($n = 17$; 39%) reported the years of wild turkey hunting experience
209 for respondents. From 1985–2000 ($n = 9$), the compiled average years of wild turkey hunting
210 experience of hunters was 11 years, meanwhile from 2001–2023 ($n = 8$) the compiled average
211 increased to 17 years. Of the studies that included both general hunting experience and wild
212 turkey hunting experience ($n = 6$), hunters had a compiled average of 11 years of wild turkey
213 hunting experience and a compiled average of 27 years of general hunting experience.

214 **Hunting practices and safety concerns**

215 General use of decoys by hunters increased throughout time (see Figure 4A), with a compiled
216 average of 83% ($n = 4$; 79% weighted) of hunters generally using decoys from 2001-2023.
217 Frequent use of decoys by hunters also increased throughout time, but more gradually (see
218 Figure 4B), with a compiled average of 57% ($n = 7$; 61% weighted) of hunters frequently using
219 decoys from 2001-2023. Of the data entries that measured safety concerns ($n = 11$; 25%), only 2
220 data entries reported that <50% of hunters were concerned about their safety; the most recent
221 study to capture this information was conducted in 2011.

222 **Study design and collaboration**

223 Most studies ($n = 25$; 78%) were designed to capture hunter's perceptions of and support for
224 hunting regulations. Additionally, most studies ($n = 19$; 59%) were designed to capture hunter's
225 perceptions of the hunt quality and their satisfaction with the hunt. Only one study included in
226 our literature review used any theoretical framework (Three-Factor Theory of Customer
227 Satisfaction; Schroeder et al. 2017) when designing their research. During 1985–2000, only 31%

228 of the studies ($n = 4$) were a collaborative effort between agencies and university researchers;
229 whereas during 2001–2023, 47% of studies ($n = 9$) were a collaborative effort. All studies
230 included in the literature review collected their data using questionnaires; no studies used
231 qualitative interviews or a mixed-methods approach.

232 **DISCUSSION**

233 The findings of our literature review indicate multiple trends: 1) the average age of wild turkey
234 hunters is increasing; 2) wild turkey hunting remains male-dominated; 3) safety concerns
235 remained consistent but have not been measured since 2011; and 4) studies incorporating
236 theoretical frameworks remain scarce. Many of these trends suggest separation of wild turkey
237 hunters from other groups of hunters and should be addressed for the long-term sustainability of
238 wild turkey hunting.

239 The 2022 National Survey of Fishing, Hunting, and Wildlife-Associated Recreation
240 estimated that the median age of U.S. hunters was 35–44 years old and 22% of hunters were
241 female (USFWS 2023). In contrast, our literature review indicates that during the past decade
242 wild turkey hunters are an average age of 50 and ~94 % male. Although the last national survey
243 examining wild turkey hunters was in 2006, findings from that survey estimated that 94% of wild
244 turkey hunters were male and that the median age of hunters was 44 (USFWS 2010), supporting
245 trends of our literature review that the average wild turkey hunter is increasing in age while
246 participation of women hunters is stationary. In contrast, the most recent national survey of
247 United States deer hunters in 2011 estimated that 88% of deer hunters were male, suggesting
248 more participation from women in deer hunting compared to wild turkey hunting (USFWS
249 2016). Furthermore, the number of deer hunters who are female slightly increased in the national
250 survey from 2006 to 2011 (91% were male in 2006; USFWS 2011, 2016). In addition, a 2021

251 survey of respondents in 19 states across the U.S. documented that of the >5000 women
252 respondents in the sample who hunt, 86% hunt deer while only 29% hunt wild turkeys (Heyser et
253 al. 2022). However, a recent study sampling women in the sports shooting and hunting
254 communities indicated that ~65% were interested in hunting wild turkeys (NWTF 2020). Thus,
255 barriers may be preventing women interested in wild turkey hunting from participating. There is
256 a need to more deeply explore barriers to recruiting new wild turkey hunters, with an emphasis
257 on examining the unique barriers to different groups of people (e.g., women, racial/ethnic
258 minorities, individuals <30 years old, etc.).

259 While our findings suggest that recruitment of new, young hunters is not offsetting the
260 aging of the current wild turkey hunting community, data is currently insufficient to dictate what
261 the overall trend is for wild turkey hunting participation. While the data from the 2011 and 2016
262 USFWS National Survey of Fishing, Hunting, and Wildlife-Associated Recreation estimated a
263 >1 million decline in wild turkey hunting participation over that five-year period, trends reported
264 from state agencies with publicly available data during that same period show that wild turkey
265 hunter numbers were increasing or stable in most of these states (see Figure S1 and Table S2).
266 Furthermore, the 2022 USFWS version of this survey did not provide an estimate of wild turkey
267 hunter participation, and more recent trends highlighted in Figure S1 suggest that, for the states
268 where estimates are accessible, most states are currently documenting an increasing or stable
269 number of wild turkey hunters. This highlights that while these national USFWS surveys do
270 provide an important estimate of trends in hunter demographics, their findings should be
271 interpreted cautiously because participation in these surveys has steadily declined during the
272 2006, 2011, and 2016 iterations, which may have impacted estimates related to wild turkey
273 hunting participation and demographics (USFWS 2018*a, b, c*). Although the trends highlighted

274 in Figure S1 do not suggest a major decrease in wild turkey hunter participation in the last 15
275 years, our findings regarding the increasing average age of a wild turkey hunter may suggest a
276 possible lag-effect or delayed decrease in wild turkey hunter participation. That is, if hunters
277 were being recruited at the same rate that they age out, we would expect the average age of the
278 hunting community to stay similar over time. Notably, the general population of the U.S has been
279 aging over the same time (1980 median age = 30; 2022 median age = 38.9; Mather &
280 Scommegna 2024), yet our review suggests that the wild turkey hunting community has aged at a
281 faster rate and is now on average ~ 10 years older than the general population. Thus, some but
282 not all of our observed aging may be explained by trends in the general population. In either
283 case, if the community continues to age, the total number of hunters must begin to decline at
284 some point in the future. Additionally, the U.S. population has increased by > 50 million in the
285 last 20 years (U.S. Census Bureau 2021), suggesting that states should be seeing proportional
286 increases in wild turkey hunter numbers, but this is inconsistent for many of the states included
287 in Figure S1. As such, future human dimensions research should continue to explore trends in
288 hunter aging and participation closely and we encourage more state agencies to collect this data
289 and make it publicly available.

290 While addressing barriers to recruiting hunters is typically approached using recruitment,
291 retention, and reactivation (R3) programs (Vayer et al. 2021; von Furstenberg et al. 2023), human
292 dimensions research also offers valuable tools to gather information about common barriers to
293 new hunters and nonhunters interested in becoming hunters. A key finding of this literature
294 review was that studies exclusively used questionnaires to gather information. No studies used
295 qualitative interviews or a mixed-methods approach to gather information about wild turkey
296 hunters. Qualitative research designs may allow for a deeper understanding of issues such as 1)

297 why many hunters participate in their first wild turkey hunt at an older age compared to other
298 species (Harmel-Garza et al. 1999); 2) why there is a gap between general hunting experience
299 and wild turkey hunting experience – suggesting either inconsistent wild turkey hunting or
300 confirming the later age in becoming a wild turkey hunter (Hunt et al. 2004, Isabelle and Reitz
301 2016); and 3) why women may be more inclined to hunt deer as opposed to wild turkey (Heyser
302 et al. 2022). While qualitative approaches have been used more broadly to assess hunter
303 recruitment and retention, many of the unique practices and traditions related to wild turkey
304 hunting likely require stand-alone research to rigorously examine barriers to becoming a wild
305 turkey hunter (Larson et al. 2014, Hansson-Forman et al. 2020).

306 Our literature review demonstrates that safety concerns have remained consistently high
307 temporally for wild turkey hunters. Furthermore, studies have indicated that safety concerns may
308 be greater for individuals hunting on public land compared to private (Vangilder et al. 1990,
309 Isabelle and Reitz 2016). Importantly, research has not been conducted to establish if safety
310 concerns may be a barrier to recruiting new wild turkey hunters. Exploring safety concerns as a
311 potential barrier should be a high priority of future human dimensions of wild turkey hunting
312 research because many agency and organization sponsored youth and introductory hunts occur
313 on public land where safety concerns appear highest (Vangilder et al. 1990, Isabelle and Reitz
314 2016). Additionally, future research should explore safety concerns related to new hunting
315 practices, such as reaping, which has recently grown in popularity like the increased broader use
316 of decoys documented in our study. Only 2 studies in our literature review directly addressed
317 reaping: 22% of hunters in a 2018 sample in South Carolina, USA, and 6% of a 2017 sample in
318 Maryland, USA, stated that they have used the fanning or reaping approach (MDNR 2017,
319 SCDNR 2018). In South Carolina, 31% of hunters in the 2018 sample stated that reaping was not

320 a safe practice across all scenarios (44% stated it was safe but only on private land) and 50%
321 believed it was a fair and ethical approach (SCNR 2018). As of 2024, 7 states have, to some
322 extent, banned reaping, mainly on public land where safety concerns are likely greatest. These
323 states are as follows: Alabama, Michigan, New Jersey, Pennsylvania, Rhode Island, South
324 Carolina, and Tennessee, USA (Weddington 2022, Simms 2023).

325 Even with new hunting practices and technology, reported wild turkey hunting incidents
326 have dramatically decreased since the 1990s (NWTF 2021*b*). Pennsylvania, which previously
327 had incident rates as high as 16.2 incidents per 100,000 hunters in fall of 1990, consistently had
328 <2 incidents per 100,000 hunters from 2007–2016 (Casalena 2018). Similarly, Missouri, which
329 once had >40 annual incidents per 100,000 wild turkey hunters, has seen a massive reduction to
330 <10 annual incidents per 100,000 hunters (Isabelle and Reitz 2016). These dramatic decreases in
331 wild turkey hunting incidents may explain why safety concerns have not been captured in human
332 dimensions of wild turkey hunting research since 2011. While wild turkeys were once one of the
333 most dangerous game species to target, modifications to hunter safety courses and disseminating
334 safety information in hunting magazines and promotional materials led to these significant
335 declines in incident rates (Langenau et al. 1985, Kantola et al. 1987, Smith et al. 2005, NWTF
336 2021*b*). However, our findings indicate that safety concerns remained elevated for wild turkey
337 hunters throughout the late 1990s and early 2000s, despite the national reduction in wild turkey
338 hunting incidents. This suggests a potential disconnect between perceived risks and actual risks
339 of wild turkey hunting that could be investigated using a human dimensions research approach.
340 Importantly, future research could explore and compare perceived risks of hunting various game
341 species to document how safety concerns vary depending on the species, then contrast these
342 findings with actual reported incidents for each species to determine if this potential disconnect

343 is displayed for multiple species. Additionally, identifying potential approaches that might
344 alleviate some of these safety concerns is critical, as much of the emphasis has been placed on
345 hunter-orange requirements. Our literature review showed that 16 of 44 data entries addressed
346 hunter-orange requirements, but few other options to address safety concerns were explored.
347 Lastly, exploring media coverage of wild turkey hunting incidents could provide additional
348 information about how this coverage influences perceived safety risks by hunters.

349 Collaborative research efforts between agencies and university researchers appear to be
350 on the rise. Prior to 2000, state agencies were largely responsible for any human dimensions of
351 wild turkey hunting research, but in the last decade this has shifted to include more collaborative
352 efforts. This collaboration is important because the diversity of perspectives can lead to more
353 comprehensive research. However, despite growing interest in human dimensions research with
354 both universities and state agencies, the increase in collaborative efforts has not translated into an
355 increase in the application of theoretical frameworks. Theoretical frameworks, especially
356 behavior changes theories, have large potential to improve our understanding of various
357 components of wild turkey hunting behavior. The complexities of behaviors such as harvesting a
358 female wild turkey in fall likely cannot be fully explored simply through stand-alone questions or
359 merely through capturing demographics and hunting motivations. Instead, assessing values,
360 beliefs, trust in government, and personal norms of hunters may be necessary to understand these
361 complex behaviors.

362 Theoretical frameworks have previously been used to assess complex pro-environmental
363 behaviors such as native plant gardening, voting intentions for wildland preservation, and
364 support for invasive species management (Vaske and Donnelly 1999, Steele et al. 2021,
365 Champine et al. 2022). Specifically, regarding hunting, the theory of planned behavior has been

366 used to assess factors influencing participation in hunting overall and deer hunting (Hrubes et al.
367 2001, Shrestha et al. 2012, Shrestha and Burns 2016). Incorporating established behavioral
368 change theories such as the theory of planned behavior allows researchers to directly examine
369 what variables influence a behavior of interest. Constructs of the social cognitive theory were
370 used to understand recruitment and retainment of female hunters and found that social support is
371 critical for both new and experienced hunters, suggesting that a reliable hunting network is
372 critical to recruiting and retaining female hunters (Smith et al. 2022). Other studies have
373 generated their own theoretical frameworks (often using constructs from other frameworks) to
374 test and apply to participation in deer hunting and assess hunters' opinions regarding harmful
375 hunting practices (Barro and Manfredo 1996, Ghasemi and Kyle 2022). Across all these hunting
376 examples applying a theoretical framework, many utilized a form of path analysis or structural
377 equation modeling to assess the relationship between different theoretical constructs. This
378 analysis method furnishes a more integrated approach that provides an understanding of both
379 direct and indirect effects of different theoretical constructs and variables to the behavior of
380 interest. This would be particularly informative to understand how different factors like years of
381 wild turkey hunting experience and level of safety concern interact with theoretical constructs
382 such as values and personal norms to influence behaviors like the decision to hunt wild turkeys
383 on public or private land and travel out of their state of residence to hunt wild turkeys.

384 Despite ~40 years of research on the human dimensions of wild turkey hunting, only 2
385 studies gathered data from western states (Arizona and Idaho). Wild turkeys were introduced to
386 many western states and may not have the same historical wild turkey hunting tradition as
387 southeastern states. However, many western states now have sizable wild turkey populations and
388 large participation in both fall and spring wild turkey hunts (Dolkas 2019, ODFW 2024). For

389 example, in spring 2022, >20,000 wild turkeys were harvested in California, USA (CDFW
390 2021). In fall 2021, >1,200 wild turkeys were harvested in Oregon, USA, and >6,000 in
391 California (CDFW 2021, ODFW 2022). The large participation in both fall and spring wild
392 turkey hunts in western states provides a great opportunity to conduct human dimensions
393 research, especially considering the unique circumstances of many of these wild turkey
394 populations. For instance, research can explore whether hunters in western states are motivated
395 from a conservation perspective to help control the population of a non-native species.
396 Additionally, research can explore the development of wild turkey hunting traditions and culture
397 in western states to compare with other regions of the U.S. like the southeast, as well as compare
398 trends in hunter participation.

399 **RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS**

400 Our literature review documents that human dimensions of wild turkey hunting research has
401 largely been conducted using questionnaires mainly focused on capturing respondent's
402 perceptions of hunting regulations and hunting quality. While these topics are critical to the
403 objectives of state agencies, expanding human dimensions of wild turkey hunting research to
404 include qualitative and mix-method approaches may allow for deeper assessment of important
405 issues such as barriers for new hunters to become wild turkey hunters; factors influencing
406 support for policy, practice, and conservation; and concern for hunter safety. Examining barriers
407 to wild turkey hunting is particularly vital because our findings indicate that the average age of
408 wild turkey hunters is progressively becoming older, while participation from women in wild
409 turkey hunting remains stationary. Understanding barriers for nontraditional pathways hunters is
410 important for addressing these trends, especially documenting if hunter safety is a barrier to
411 welcoming more new wild turkey hunters. Additionally, expanding qualitative and quantitative

412 research to utilize theoretical frameworks may provide a more thorough understanding of
413 complex behaviors and more rigorously assess support for different hunting regulations. Lastly,
414 our findings revealed a large regional bias in human dimensions of wild turkey hunting research,
415 with only 2 studies including data from a western state. Expanding the scope of human
416 dimensions of wild turkey hunting to include more western states may provide an opportunity to
417 explore the rapidly developing wild turkey hunting populations in these states.

418 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

419 We would like to thank B. Long for providing access to the findings of a 2007 Maryland hunter
420 survey. We would like to thank A.D. Holmes, D.J.E. Sturgeon, and M.A. Turner for providing
421 helpful feedback and encouragement regarding this manuscript. Additionally, we would like to
422 thank the University of Florida Libraries team for providing access to several articles used in this
423 literature review. We would like to thank the following state agencies for making wild turkey
424 hunter numbers used in Figure S1 publicly available on their website, or for kindly providing this
425 data via personal email: Alabama Department of Conservation and Natural Resources – Wildlife
426 and Freshwater Fisheries Division, Georgia Department of Natural Resources – Wildlife
427 Resources Division, Indiana Department of Natural Resources – Division of Fish and Wildlife,
428 Kansas Department of Wildlife and Parks, Louisiana Department of Wildlife and Fisheries,
429 Nebraska Game and Parks Commission, North Carolina Wildlife Resources Commission –
430 Wildlife Management Division, Oklahoma Department of Wildlife Conservation, Pennsylvania
431 Game Commission – Bureau of Wildlife Management, South Carolina Department of Natural
432 Resources, and Texas Parks and Wildlife Department. Special thanks to C. Gizel and H.
433 Plumpton for their assistance with completing datasets.

434 **ETHICS STATEMENT**

435 No ethical information provided.

436 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST**

437 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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657

658 Figure 1. Representation of different states in the United States with human dimensions studies
 659 of wild turkey research from 1985–2023. Some studies reported data from separate data
 660 collection in multiple states or from separate data collection from multiple years for a single
 661 state; therefore, each time a state was represented in a study was counted as a unique data entry.

662

663 Figure 2. Average age of respondents throughout time for the different data entries included in
 664 the literature review of wild turkey human dimensions research. Each point represents a unique
 665 data entry. For data entries spanning multiple years, the midpoint of these years was used for the
 666 point. A trendline is included (gray, dashed line) to highlight the trend of average wild turkey
 667 hunter age from 1985 to 2023.

668

669 Figure 3. Average age of respondents representing wild turkey hunters across time for: 1)
 670 Pennsylvania; 2) Virginia; 3) Missouri; and 4) Mississippi, USA. Each point represents a unique
 671 data entry and only states with ≥ 3 data entries of average hunter age were included. For data
 672 entries spanning multiple years, the midpoint of these years was used for the point.

673

674 Figure 4. Percentage of respondents in sample generally using decoys (A) and frequently using
 675 decoys (B) for hunting wild turkeys across time for the different data entries included in the
 676 literature review. General use of decoys corresponds to hunters who reported using decoys at
 677 least rarely or occasionally, whereas frequent use of decoys corresponds to hunters who reported
 678 using decoys at high volume (e.g., always, mostly, often, etc.; see Methods). Each point
 679 represents a unique data entry. For data entries spanning multiple years, the midpoint of these
 680 years was used for the point. A trendline is included (gray, dashed line) to highlight the trend of
 681 decoy use.

682

683 Figure 5. Percentage of respondents in sample frequently using decoys for hunting wild turkeys
 684 across time for South Dakota and Missouri, USA. Frequent use of decoys corresponds to hunters
 685 who reported using decoys at high volume (e.g., always, mostly, often, etc.; see Methods). Each
 686 point represents a unique data entry and only states with ≥ 3 data entries of percentage of
 687 respondents using decoys were included. For data entries spanning multiple years, the midpoint
 688 of these years was used for the point.